

THE ESSENCE AND NECESSITY OF DEVELOPING THE TRADE SERVICES SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14602022>

Abstract. *This article addresses the essence and necessity of developing the trade services system, improving the organizational-economic mechanisms for the development of trade services, ensuring the strategic competitiveness of trade enterprises, and developing the theoretical and methodological aspects of forming competition strategies. Additionally, it offers ways to improve the service provision in trade and takes into account the characteristics of the service sector.*

Keywords: *economy, market economy, modernization, competitiveness, service provision, trade services, trade enterprises, free trade.*

Introduction

In the formation of the new economy of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the issues of improving the organizational and economic mechanisms for the development of trade services, among measures to modernize its leading industries and sectors and increasing their competitiveness. The development strategy of New Uzbekistan for the period 2022-2026 defines the task of "increasing the volume of services by 3 times in the next 5 years and creating a total of 3.5 million new jobs in this area" [1]. Also, with the comprehensive development of trade services, which are considered the main type of services in the republic, especially when implementing structural changes and diversifying the industry, issues such as the organization of "digital trade" that ensures quality satisfaction are addressed. Growing consumer needs and the formation of a trade cluster taking into account the needs of the region are among the priority tasks. All this requires an in-depth study of the issues of organizational and economic mechanisms for the development of trade services, which are considered the main sector of the republic's economy, as well as the development of medium-term forecast parameters and forecast indicators for the development of "digital trade" services.

Analysis of literature on the topic

The development of trade services and their role in a market economy has been studied by many different researchers. In particular, P. Samuelson [2], F. Kotler [3] studied the theoretical foundations of the development of trade services from foreign scientists, leading scientists of the CIS countries, such as F. Pankratova [4], K. Raisky [5] to improve the efficiency of trade and propose different models for achieving it. Of the Uzbek scientists, B. Abdukarimov [6] improved the institutional and economic foundations for the development of trade services in Uzbekistan, M. M. Mukhammedov [7] developed a system of indicators reflecting the development of trade services and the methodological basis for its assessment, I. Ivatov [8] formed the market for trade services and studied the possibilities of increasing industry revenues based on its diversification. Also, a number of scientists have conducted in-depth studies of the evolution of trade services and

the problems of trade development in modern market relations. Currently, the lack of research related to the field of trade services has led to the need to prepare a scientific article on this topic.

Research methodology

The theoretical and methodological basis of the research article are fundamental scientific and practical works of the classics of economics, works of leading domestic and foreign scientists on the problem under study, developments of specialized research and trade organizations on the problems of exploitation and the system of state regulation of trade development, international materials of republican and regional scientific and practical conferences and seminars, publications in periodical scientific journals, regulatory documents in the field of state regulation of trade development, the Republic and the executive power and regional trade management programs.

Analysis and results

The development of trade services is of great importance in the development of mankind and is closely related to the development of world civilization. Being one of the centers of world civilization, Central Asia, especially Uzbekistan, passing through the "Great Silk Road", occupied a significant place in the history of the development of international trade relations. The history of the development of trade and economic relations and trade services in the regions of Central Asia is scientifically substantiated by the fact that it is divided into certain stages describing the peaks of its growth and crisis processes and associated with the development of mankind. Especially in its last period, that is, from 1991 to the present day, after the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence, a completely new era began in the sphere of trade services, which was expressed in the establishment of a free trade system based on the need to form unique trade services as an independent state.

According to international experience, the development of the trade sphere is carried out in private, collective, individual, state and mixed forms. Trade is an integral part of the market economy and, as an important sector of the "Market", performs the perfect function of delivering consumer goods from production to consumers through the trade process. All elements of the market participate in the trade process, i.e. supply and demand, prices, and the activities of these elements are coordinated through competition.

It should be noted that international trade and capital movement, trade investments, and development of information technologies affect the rate of economic growth of countries in the context of globalization. As a result, opportunities arise for modernization of trade networks, technical and technological re-equipment. In this regard, there is a need to form a system of trade services directly related to the economic development of our Republic. This need is expressed in the following:

- ensures social protection of the population through high-quality trade services.
- encourages people to receive high incomes, that is, works on the principle of "high income - a guarantee of high sales".
- emphasizes that the sale of high-quality products is the key to a long human life;
- indicates that high-quality trade services are an important basis for replenishing the state budget;
- it is important to establish that the rational organization of trade services is an important basis for ensuring employment of the population of the republic.

New priority economic reforms implemented in the context of innovative development of the Republic of Uzbekistan open up broad opportunities for the emergence of new economic

relations and new modern forms and methods, i.e. "Internet trade", "online trade" in increasing the efficiency of trade services. Socio-economic progress, development of technology, in particular, improving the well-being of our people, as well as improving the material and spiritual needs of the population are directly related to trade services. It is known that the economic reforms implemented in Uzbekistan are aimed at increasing the efficiency of the national economy. The systematic formation of the trade services sector, which is considered an integral part of the economy of our republic, creates new economic opportunities.

Therefore, based on the above, the main goal of the current stage of economic transformations is to create favorable conditions for the effective operation of trade enterprises. The complexity of the goals determines the need for a thorough study of the essence and content of the concept of trade services, which become a key link in the market mechanism of the network as an independent economic entity. It is known that the emergence of trade is associated with the creation of commodity production and commodity circulation, exchange as a result of the social division of labor. Trade services are the main segment of the consumer goods market. Provides services to individuals and legal entities. With its help, the population and enterprises, organizations and institutions satisfy their needs for certain goods. There are trade relations between sellers and consumers: the owner of money receives goods, and the owner of goods receives money.

Trade services are explained by the fact that they are aimed at improving people's lives, providing employment for the population, and increasing their well-being by increasing income. Therefore, the importance of the trade sector, which is considered an important branch of the economy in improving the quality of life of the population is incomparable. The most important thing is that its development directly affects the demands and needs of consumers. Such conditions are important for improving the quality of services of trade enterprises. The quality of trade services depends on the state of its material and technical base and the structure of its infrastructure. The republic has sufficient potential for further improvement of the state and infrastructure of the trade, material and technical base. Analysis of the economic state of services, their provision and efficiency is of great socio-economic importance for each commercial enterprise. After all, the wealth of each commercial enterprise is part of the wealth of society, and no one has the right to be indifferent to it.

Therefore, regardless of the form of ownership, the analysis of indicators reflecting the economic potential of a trading enterprise should constitute the main part of trade. The analysis shows that the most important tasks of trade services are to ensure communication between manufacturing enterprises and customers, facilitate financing and planning of the production process based on the order system, form an optimal inventory, provide information to the manufacturer about the needs of consumers, as well as ensure stable growth of the manufacturing enterprise and ensure high economic efficiency.

The rapid development of the service sector in Uzbekistan, the increase in the role and share of services in the formation of the gross domestic product, a radical change in the composition of the services provided, primarily due to their modern high-tech types are indicated as special goals in the development strategy. In this "Development Strategy" as a result of "Development of the service sector" [1] it is noted that "to increase the volume of services by 3 times in the next 5 years" and "to reduce the share of the hidden economy 3 times in the service sector" as the most important task.

It should be noted that from a scientific, socio-economic point of view, scientific works, educational and popular literature contain various scientific opinions on the trading process, trade services, the market and trade. In this regard, F. Kotler [3,89], the world's leading marketer, characterizes the market as "a complex of existing and potential buyers of goods." Also, another group of leading economists of the world, K.R. McConnell and S.L. Brewer, call "the market and trade, goods and services as interconnected components, a mechanism linking sellers and buyers" [9,56]. In this regard, the American scientist P. Samuelson in his work "Economics" defines the market as "... markets act as a mechanism linking society and commercial production activity" [2,77].

From Russian scientists, N.Ushakova and Yu.A. Avanesova define trade services as follows, in their opinion, "Trade services are the final function of trade, consisting in the sale of goods and the provision of services to customers through retail trade" [10,35].

Based on the theories of international trade described above, scientists in this field in Uzbekistan have conducted in-depth scientific research and expressed a number of their scientific views. One of the economists, N. Tukhliev believes that "the market is the sum of trade and exchange, commodity and monetary relations of circulation, organized on the basis of the laws of commodity production, and is an important link between production and consumption" [11,13].

B.A. Abdukarimov, who has been conducting research in this area for many years, noted: "Trade is a special type of service that serves producers, on the one hand, and consumers, on the other, and the state, on the third hand, and, fourthly, it also serves other industries and sectors of the economy, the consumer of their services uses and communicates with them" [6,42]. According to Professor I. Ivatov, "The essence of trade is reflected in the emergence of economic laws that develop society. Therefore, based on trade management, it is necessary to be able to objectively see the requirements of economic laws and make decisions based on them" [8,22]. Professor K. Mirzayev also believes that "it is necessary to determine the economic processes (real phenomena) that are formed in trading activities, by what means they are created in this area" [12,65].

It should be noted that the number of economists in our republic represent the trade process directly related to the market. In their opinion, the market is a set of relations between producers and consumers (sellers and buyers) that arise in the process of exchange by means of money, especially in this process "manufactured goods stores, retail outlets, various supermarkets, large shopping centers and shopping centers, fairs, catering outlets are typical types of markets".

Summary.

We presented our scientific findings based on the results of an in-depth scientific study of the above-described theories of international trade, as well as a number of scientific views and scientific opinions in this direction. According to our scientific conclusion, the author's definitions of the concepts of "trade services" and "efficiency of trade services" are presented.

In the modern new economy of Uzbekistan, in the context of fundamental structural changes, the study of the activities of trade enterprises, conducting scientific research on trade services, identifying their problems, finding their solutions is a complex process, and we believe that the following is necessary to solve them:

to find out on a scientific basis the origin and nature of trade and use it in the development of the trade economy of our republic;

to determine the role and importance of trade in society and develop directions for increasing its efficiency;

to identify economic, organizational and managerial problems arising in trade, and to make scientific proposals for their solution. This requires deep knowledge of economic relations in the trade process, its economic mechanism, reveals the internal possibilities of trade services;

to organize high-quality trade, digitalization of trade and development of trade enterprises and industries, analysis of trends and development of scientific proposals for its further development;

it consists in the analysis of advanced foreign experience in the organization of trade services, development of mechanisms for their use from their positive and suitable sides for the economy of our republic.

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